

Scoring system for carbon storage capacity in European marine biogenic habitats and beyond

Deliverable 4.4

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The MPA Europe project

MPA Europe is a project co-funded by the European Union (EU) that will map a network of locations representative of biodiversity in European seas (Atlantic Exclusive Economic Zones of the EU and its neighbours, and all the Mediterranean, Baltic, and Black seas) (Figure A).

Figure A. MPA Europe study area.

This network will indicate where to prioritise placement of Marine Protected Areas (MPA) for biodiversity protection and how Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) can maximise blue carbon benefits. By using a holistic set of biodiversity measures, from species to ecosystems (including habitats), and environmental data including carbon storage, water currents, and climate change velocity models, it will be possible to quantify and map both the present and future connectivity within the proposed MPA network. The multiple scenarios provided will support wider and improved MSP by policy makers, industry, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs). The major scientific areas of the project and its outcomes are summarized in the infographic presented in Figure Figure B.

Figure B. MPA Europe project scientific areas

The inter-disciplinary approach of MPA Europe is supported by a diversity of partners. These include Nord University (Norway), the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO (Belgium), Aarhus University (Denmark), Climazul (Greece), the Centre of Marine Sciences (Portugal), Science Crunchers (Portugal), the Joint Nature Conservation Committee (England, UK), the Scottish Association for Marine Science (Scotland, UK), the Ocean University of China (China), and the University of the Ryukyus (Japan). The partners include experts in marine biology, taxonomy, ecology, oceanography, biogeochemistry, and biogeography, MPA network design, benthic habitat mapping, carbon dynamics, species distribution, climate modelling, and MSP compose the MPA Europe team.

Deliverable 4.4 overview

This report describes a Blue Carbon scoring system and the methods behind this system, which will be used to rank carbon storage capacity in European seas. Based on the sediment organic carbon (OC) data compiled and presented in **Deliverable 4.1** (*Database of estimated carbon storage in European marine biogenic habitats*, Graversen et al. 2023a) and **Deliverable 4.2** (*Database of carbon storage in European marine non-biogenic sediment habitats*, Graversen et al. 2023b), we propose a 5-level scoring system that can be applied across European seas based on the weighted averages of %OC for the top 10 cm sediment. Our Blue Carbon Index (BCI) provides a preliminary score across European sea basins based on the “quantiles of 20%” of sediment OC observations described in Deliverable 4.1 and 4.2. In addition, information from the four most important environmental predictors of OC content identified in **Deliverable 4.3** (Lønborg et al. 2024) as well as information about biogenic and non-biogenic substrata and vegetated habitats associated with our observed OC values are used to gain knowledge about characteristics associated with the five scores of OC content.

The BCI allows us to classify the “Blue Carbon” levels of different sea basins, which is the focus of a subsequent task (**Deliverable 4.5**). This information will be compared with the biodiversity maps (WP3) to further understanding of the relationships between marine biodiversity and carbon content of the seafloor, and guide the prioritization of marine protected areas (WP5).

Introduction

Blue Carbon refers to marine sediment organic carbon (OC) that is captured and stored by the oceans and coastal ecosystems, especially in vegetated coastal ecosystems such as seagrass meadows, tidal marshes, and mangrove forests. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) has defined Blue Carbon as “*all biologically driven carbon fluxes and storage in marine systems that are amenable to management*”. Blue Carbon research has traditionally mainly focused on the role of management of vegetated coastal habitats to protect and increase their capacity to capture carbon dioxide and retain OC while also supporting biodiversity and other key ecological functions (Duarte et al. 2013; Howard et al. 2014; Nellemann et al. 2009). The challenges and opportunities of such Blue Carbon strategies were recently summarised (Gattuso et al. 2023). The Blue Carbon concept is expanding, and marine sediments are categorised as “emerging Blue Carbon ecosystems” where human action may be able to increase these sinks by protecting the seafloor from disturbance (Howard et al. 2023, Epstein et al 2022). In addition to studies focusing on how protection may affect marine sediment OC, there is a need for a robust understanding of the factors controlling OC levels, and for simple scoring systems allowing a classification of sediment Blue Carbon levels across sea basins. In this report we present a Blue Carbon Index (BCI), which scores the level of OC in sediments (top 10 cm) of European Seas on a 5-level scale. This information can be used to optimise Marine Spatial Planning by indicating where marine protected areas (MPAs) would benefit carbon storage in addition to biodiversity.

Methods

Data included

The data used for the scoring system is based on the datasets described in Deliverable 4.1 (Graversen et al. 2023a) and Deliverable 4.2 (Graversen et al. 2023b), and on the additional information gained in Deliverable 4.3 (Lønborg et al. 2024). In Deliverable 4.1 and Deliverable 4.2 we compiled a dataset consisting of ~25,000 observations of directly determined sediment % total organic carbon (%OC) values. In addition to OC values, ancillary data including dry bulk density, water depth, and OC-accumulation rates (where available), were provided by data contributors, (see Deliverable 4.1). Deliverable 4.3 provides additional details on the weighted averages of %OC (~6000 averaged TOC values) for the top 10 cm sediment in different sediments and habitats, and on environmental variables associated with the locations (e.g., coastal exposure, temperature, etc.).

Developing a scoring system for carbon storage capacity: The development of a scoring system can be based on multiple approaches and methods, using for example approaches from the literature reference such as quantiles of the data (e.g. see Gasca-Aragon & Duewer, 2016; Gu et al. 2019). We have for this report tested several approaches and selected the scoring system that best reflects the Blue Carbon levels observed across European Seas. It should here be noted that our scoring system will be updated once the database, described in Deliverable 4.1 and Deliverable 4.2, is finalised and the analysis presented in Deliverable 4.3 is updated.

Characteristics associated with the scoring system of OC content:

The statistical analysis presented in Deliverable 4.3 (Lønborg et al. 2024), identified the key environmental factors related to sediment OC levels on a European sea basins scale. Those variables are therefore expected to best describe the characteristics within each score of the Blue Carbon Index (BCI). Accordingly, environmental data associated to our observed OC values from the four most important environmental variables (coastal exposure, distance to coast, temperature and bathymetry)

are used in this deliverable to characterize each of the scoring classes within the BCI. Finally, the BCI scores are also characterised based on substratum information and presence of biogenic vs. non-biogenic habitats.

For the purposes of this report, we used the European broad-scale seabed habitat map (EUSeaMap) classification for seabed substrata that are defined according to the Folk 7 sediment triangle, plus biogenic substrata (see Deliverable 4.3, Appendix 1). Although the European Nature Information System (EUNIS) classification refers to “biogenic habitat”, the EMODnet Seabed Habitats consortium has agreed on referring to “biogenic substratum” to highlight that this is specifically about substratum-modifying features. Therefore, “biogenic substratum” strictly refers to beds or reefs of a species such as *Limaria hians* beds, *Modiolus modiolus* beds, *Posidonia oceanica* meadows, *Serpula vermicularis* reefs, which is compatible with the term used in the EUNIS v2022 habitat classification system (see Deliverable 4.3, Appendix 1; Lillis et al., 2021).

Results and Discussion

Developing a scoring system for carbon storage capacity

The development of the BCI is based on a five-points scale to assess %OC, ranging from “1” associated with very low levels to “5” associated with very high %OC content. This classification is derived from the observed distribution of weighted average %OC values from the top 10 cm of marine sediments (Figure 1).

Given that the majority (70%) of OC observations fall within the range of 0-2 %OC, the proposed BCI is based on the quantiles of 20% of the frequency distribution of the data, which are used to divide the dataset into five classes, containing an equal number of observations within each (Table 1).

We compared score-classes based on different scaling methods, including a logarithm scale, a linear scale based on equal interval of observations with a fixed maximum, and a scale with finer intervals at lower OC values and coarser scale at higher OC values (see Table 1) to resolve potential differences and select the best scoring system. A scoring system based on the logarithmic scale resulted in most observations being associated with score 3 or 4 while a system based on a linear scale resulted in most observations being associated with score 1 or 2 (Table 1).

Although all mentioned scaling methods are valid, our proposed BCI score is the one that assigns the most nuanced scoring and thus reflects the distribution of available datapoints at current state the best. This scoring system was also compared to the OC-classes defined by Premuzic et al. (1980, 1982), which divided the global distribution of OC in the surficial sediments into five classes and showed similarities to our proposed BCI scoring system (see Figure 2, Table 1).

Characteristics associated with the BCI scores

All marine regions were present in BCI 1, while either the Black Sea or the High Seas was not present in the rest of the BCI scores (Figure 3). In addition, there was an unequal data distribution among the four marine regions with the Northeast Atlantic Ocean constituting the majority of data (78%), followed by the Mediterranean Sea (15%), Baltic Sea (6%), the Black Sea (0.4%), and the High Seas (0.6%). Even though most data represented the Northeast Atlantic Ocean across all scores, the low BCI scores were associated with more data from the High Seas and Black Seas compared to the high and very high BCI scores 4 and 5, which included no data from these marine regions.

When considering the part of the dataset associated with biogenic substrata (67 observations), the most dominant biogenic substratum *Posidonia oceanica* was associated with the BCI 5, both count-wise and percentage-wise (88%) (Figure 4). The three other biogenic habitats present in the dataset, *Modiolus modiolus* beds, *Serpula vermicularis* reefs and *Limaria hians* beds, were mainly associated with BCI 1 (40%) (Figure 4).

Sand comprised 28 % of the non-biogenic substrata observations associated with BCI 1 (Figure 5). The percentage of sand decreased with increasing BCI score (BCI 2: 8%, BCI 3: 7%, BCI 4: 3%) with only 2% of sand being present in BCI 5. Similarly, the presence of the substratum type “muddy sand” decreased from BCI 1 (12 %) to BCI 5 (5%), and “coarse substrate” also decreased from BCI 1 (9%) to BCI 5 (1%). These are all coarser-grained substrata compared to “fine mud”, “sandy mud”, “fine mud or sandy mud or muddy sand and sandy mud” and “muddy sand” that together make up a larger percentage of BCI scores 2, 3, 4 and 5, as compared to BCI 1. In general, there is a pattern of coarser sediment being linked with lower BCI scores and finer sediment linked to higher BCI scores. However, it should be noted that the distribution of marine substrata is currently incomplete due to limited information.

From the previous study on environmental drivers of OC levels in marine sediments (see Deliverable 4.3, Lønborg et al. 2024), coastal wave exposure was clearly the most important (describing 24% of the variability in OC levels), followed by maximum temperature (20%), distance from shore (16%), and water depth (9%) (see Deliverable 4.3). However, among these four environmental variables only coastal exposure, showed a link to the BCI scores with more exposed areas generally having lower BCI score (Figure 8). Both the highest (BCI 5) and lowest (BCI 1) BCI scores were associated with higher water temperatures and shallower water depths (Figure 8, Table 5).

BCI scores across vegetated habitats

The BCI scores associated with seagrass meadows had an uneven distribution with most observations associated with the BCI 1 and 5 (Figure 6). A similar distribution of observations across BCI scores were seen for saltmarshes (i.e., 40% in BCI 5; 38% in BCI 1; 12% in BCI 4; 9% in BCI 3; and 1% in BCI 2). However, it should here be noted that substrata for saltmarshes could not be evaluated since these grow in the transition zone between land and sea and therefore were not assigned to any EUSeaMap substrata.

Our dataset showed a high variability in the association between vegetation species and substrata (see Figure 7). Here *Cymodocea nodosa* is mostly associated with “sandy mud”, *Nanozostera noltei* with “muddy sand”, *Posidonia oceanica* with “*Posidonia oceanica* meadows”, and *Zostera marina* with “fine mud”. Such difference in substratum can together with other biological and environmental factors influence the amount of %OC stored (see e.g. Samper-Villarreal et al. 2016; Stankovic et al. 2017; Tahir et al. 2023). Hence, complex interactions between seagrass structure (e.g. species, size, density), with environmental factors (e.g. light water depth, turbidity, and wave height) influence OC levels in seagrass sediments (Kennedy et al. 2022; Samper-Villarreal et al. 2016; Stankovic et al. 2017; Tahir et al. 2023).

“Coarse” substrate was the dominant substratum for seagrasses with BCI 1 (Figure 6), “sandy mud” and “fine mud or sandy mud or muddy sand” were mainly found in BCI 2, “*Posidonia oceanica* meadows” was the dominant substratum in BCI 3 (22%), while BCI 4 and 5 had most OC

observations in “sandy mud” (22%) and “fine mud” (13%). However, the distribution of marine substrata is incomplete due to limited information.

Among the four most important environmental variables (coastal exposure, distance to coast, temperature and bathymetry) associated to our observed OC seagrass values (see Deliverable 4.3., Lønborg et al. 2024), only coastal exposure, showed a trend across the BCI scores, with more exposed areas having a lower BCI score (Figure 9, Table 2).

Conclusion

We tested several potential blue carbon scoring systems to assign blue carbon scores to observations of %OC of surface sediments (top 10 cm) of European Seas. Our final Blue Carbon Index scoring system (BCI) was created in order to distribute scores evenly across the observations, resulting in a scale that divided the axis in finer intervals at low OC values and coarser divisions towards the high OC values. For each BCI score we explored the characteristics of environmental drivers as well as information about marine region, biogenic substrata, non-biogenic substrata and vegetated habitats, and found that high BCI scores were more associated with finer sediment and lower coastal exposure than lower BCI scores. However, it should be noted that these patterns were not clear and the variation within each score was high. The final division of scores need to be adjusted according to the final dataset.

Next steps:

- Combine the five BCI classes with the predicted OC values generated by the XGBoost model to be able to predict and classify the OC content for the European Sea basins than limiting the scoring to only the observed OC values. This will be included in next Deliverable 4.5.
- Update the BCI scores once the database, described in Deliverable 4.1 and Deliverable 4.2, is finalised.
- Include EUSeaMap substrata, and seafloor depressions and potentially additional variables as environmental predictors in the XGBoost model presented in Deliverable 4.3.

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Table 1. Table of different Blue Carbon scoring system, range of values per score and the associated organic carbon datapoints.

SCORE	1	2	3	4	5
Definition	Very low	Low	Moderate	High	Very high
Blue Carbon Index (BCI) (20% quantiles)	0-0.4	0.4-0.8	0.8-1.5	1.5-2.5	>2.5
Datapoints	1303	1340	1320	1333	1325
Log scale	0-0.01	0.01-0.1	0.1-1	1-10	>10
Datapoints	9	208	2810	3524	70
Linear scale with max=10%	0-2.5	2.5-5	5-7.5	7.5-10	>10
Datapoints	5344	846	271	90	70
Linear scale with max=5%	0-1.25	1.25-2.5	2.5-3.75	3.75-5	>5
Datapoints	3490	1854	543	303	431
Finer start, coarser end	0-0.5	0.5-1	1-2.5	2.5-5	>5
Datapoints	1584	1443	2317	846	431
Premuzic et al. (1982)	<0.25	0.25-0.5	0.51-1	1.01-2	>2
Datapoints	691	893	1443	1616	1978

Table 2. Descriptive statistics for the environmental data (Coastal exposure (CE), Temperature max (TM), Distance to coast (DC) and Water depth (WD)) of non-biogenic substrata (left) and substrata associated to seagrass meadows (right) from the averaged top 10 cm. The minimum, 1st (25 percentage) quartile, average values, median, 3rd (75 percentage) quartile and maximum are shown for each blue carbon index (BCI) score

BCI Score	Environmental variable	Non-biogenic substrata						Seagrass meadows' substrata					
		Min	1st quartile	Median	Mean	3rd quartile	Max	Min	1st quartile	Median	Mean	3rd quartile	Max
1	Coastal exposure (CE)	2.06	3.25	3.85	3.67	4.15	4.60	2.22	3.26	3.75	3.58	3.89	4.35
2	Coastal exposure (CE)	2.24	3.31	3.91	3.78	4.32	4.54	2.24	2.99	3.68	3.50	4.01	4.38
3	Coastal exposure (CE)	2.06	3.14	3.68	3.62	4.17	4.55	2.61	2.94	3.68	3.55	4.11	4.37
4	Coastal exposure (CE)	2.06	3.02	3.44	3.48	3.92	4.52	2.39	2.94	3.40	3.53	4.31	4.38
5	Coastal exposure (CE)	2.06	2.71	3.08	3.24	3.82	4.51	2.06	2.62	2.92	3.21	4.23	4.45
1	Temperature max (TM)	-0.90	12.50	14.60	15.30	18.90	27.90	12.60	18.20	19.00	19.90	21.80	27.50
2	Temperature max (TM)	-1.00	8.90	13.10	12.70	15.10	27.80	14.10	18.80	19.30	20.60	21.90	27.50
3	Temperature max (TM)	-1.00	8.10	12.70	11.90	15.00	27.70	15.70	18.80	19.30	20.40	22.00	27.50
4	Temperature max (TM)	-0.20	7.70	10.50	11.70	14.90	27.30	15.70	18.30	19.00	20.00	22.20	27.30
5	Temperature max (TM)	0.90	13.60	15.70	15.80	18.60	27.30	14.00	18.10	18.90	19.50	19.60	27.30
1	Distance to coast (DC)	0.90	286.00	2198.00	32600.00	23380.00	996456.00	1.00	84.00	186.00	283.00	404.00	1652.00
2	Distance to coast (DC)	0.90	1216.00	6489.00	43174.00	55390.00	1019240.00	1.00	90.00	157.00	343.00	413.00	1652.00
3	Distance to coast (DC)	0.90	765.00	5539.00	30921.00	37357.00	794184.00	1.00	57.00	115.00	328.00	386.00	2996.00
4	Distance to coast (DC)	0.90	554.00	5042.00	17646.00	14162.00	337298.00	1.00	75.00	263.00	617.00	632.00	2996.00
5	Distance to coast (DC)	0.70	138.00	398.00	6734.00	1112.00	397031.00	0.70	56.00	100.00	481.00	288.00	5028.00
1	Water depth (WD)	-4823.00	-99.00	-40.00	-177.00	-5.00	1.00	-35.00	-8.00	-3.00	-6.00	-2.00	0.00
2	Water depth (WD)	-5079.00	-374.00	-102.00	-514.00	-35.00	0.00	-35.00	-13.00	-2.00	-7.00	-1.00	0.00
3	Water depth (WD)	-5416.00	-320.00	-106.00	-448.00	-34.00	1.00	-21.00	-11.00	-2.00	-6.00	-1.00	0.00
4	Water depth (WD)	-5576.00	-355.00	-212.00	-307.00	-50.00	1.00	-20.00	-12.00	-2.00	-6.00	-1.00	0.00
5	Water depth (WD)	-3142.00	-69.00	-32.00	-71.00	-5.00	1.00	-30.00	-4.00	-2.00	-5.00	-2.00	0.00

Figure 1. Frequency plot of the weighted averaged % organic carbon (OC (%)) content in the top 10 cm of sediment.

Figure 2. Distribution of % organic carbon in the surficial sediments of world oceans and seas. Source (Premuzic et al., 1982).

Marine regions

Figure 3. Stacked barplot (left) and associated table (right) illustrating the scoring distribution for all weighted averaged organic carbon (OC) observations in count (A) and percentage (B) associated with European marine regions, respectively. Each bar represents a blue carbon index (BCI) score and within each bar the stacks are divided and coloured by marine region.

Figure 4. Stacked barplots (left) and associated table (right) illustrating the scoring distribution for all weighted averaged organic carbon (OC) observations in count (A) and percentage (B) associated with EUSeaMap biogenic substrata, respectively. Each bar represents a blue carbon index (BCI) score and within each bar the stacks are divided and coloured by EUSeaMap biogenic substrata.

Non-biogenic substrata

B)

Substratum type	BCI Score				
	1	2	3	4	5
Fine mud	4.5	15.0	15	41.4	15.3
Sandy mud	19.3	23.3	21.3	13.9	10.8
Fine mud or Sandy mud or Muddy sand	0.4	0.1	0.2	0.9	5.2
Sandy mud or muddy sand	1.1	1.9	0.6	0.2	0
Muddy sand	11.5	11.0	9.1	2.6	5.0
Sand	27.9	7.7	7.4	2.9	2.2
Coarse substrate	9.1	3.9	2.1	0.8	1.1
Coarse and mixed sediment	0.1	0.4	0.2	0.2	1.1
Mixed sediment	3.2	1.6	1.9	1.7	4.6
NA	23	35.2	42.4	35.4	54.8

Figure 5. Stacked barplots (left) and associated table (right) illustrating the scoring distribution for all weighted averaged organic carbon (OC) observations in count (A) and percentage (B) associated with non-biogenic substrata, respectively. Each bar represents a blue carbon index (BCI) score and within each bar the stacks are divided and coloured by EUSeaMap non-biogenic substrata.

Figure 6. Stacked barplot (left) and associated table (right) illustrating the scoring distribution for all weighted averaged organic carbon (OC) observations in count (A) and percentage (B) associated with the vegetated blue carbon habitat seagrass meadows, respectively. *Cymodocea*, *Posidonia*, *Nanozostera*, and *Zostera* species are included as seagrass meadow. Each bar represents a blue carbon index (BCI) score and within each bar the stacks are divided and coloured by EUSeaMap substrata

Figure 7. Sankey diagram illustrating the distribution of vegetation and its associated marine substratum in the blue organic carbon (OC) dataset. Non-reported seagrass species indicates the presence of seagrass meadows with lack of information at species level. The right column represents the blue carbon index (BCI) score.

Non-biogenic substrata

Figure 8. Boxplots showing the distribution of each of the 4 key environmental variables identified as potential drivers for organic carbon (OC) scores: (A) coastal exposure, (B) temperature max, (C) distance to coast, (D) water depth across the 5 scores of blue carbon index (BCI) for the averaged top 10 cm sediment associated to non-biogenic substrata (top) and to seagrass meadows (bottom). The lines represent median values, the limits of the boxes represent 1st-3rd percentiles, and the whiskers extend from the limit of the box to the largest or smallest value but no further than 1.5*IQR (inter quartile range). Note: the water depth data is provided by data contributors, except for few cases where the lack of information was filled by modelled bathymetry data from Bio-Oracle v3.

Seagrass meadows' substrata

Figure 9. Boxplots showing the distribution of each of the 4 key environmental variables identified as potential drivers for organic carbon (OC) scores: (A) coastal exposure, (B) temperature max, (C) distance to coast, (D) water depth across the 5 scores of blue carbon index (BCI) for the averaged top 10 cm sediment associated to seagrass meadows. The lines represent median values, the limits of the boxes represent 1st-3rd percentiles, and the whiskers extend from the limit of the box to the largest or smallest value but no further than 1.5*IQR (inter quartile range). Note: the water depth data is provided by data contributors, except for few cases where the lack of information was filled by modelled bathymetry data from Bio-Oracle v3.

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